

**Research Link
Australia
Dashboard Workshop Report**

Contents

Introduction	3
User Requirements Workshop	3
About the workshop	3
Insights	3
How these insights are incorporated into future work	4
Demonstration Workshop	6
About the workshop	6
Insights	6
How these insights are incorporated into future work	6
Conclusion and Future Direction	6

Introduction

The Research Link Australia (RLA) project, supported by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), aims to bridge gaps in research collaboration by developing a national platform to aggregate, analyse, and share insights about research expertise, outcomes, and partnerships. This report outlines key findings and progress from two significant workshops: the User Requirements Workshop and the Demonstration Workshop. The User Requirements Workshop identifies the needs of stakeholders such as research managers and commercialisation officers to inform the design of the Analytical Interface Toolkit (AIT). The demonstration Workshop highlighted advancements in the AIT and explored the potential of integrating Large Language Models for enhanced data interaction. These activities have laid the groundwork for creating tools that address collaboration challenges, and promote data-drive decision-making across academic, government, and industry.

User Requirements Workshop

The first User Requirements Workshop occurred on Friday, 13th of September 2024. It involved participants from Griffith University, University of Technology Sydney (UTS), Southern Cross University (SCU), and ARDC.

The workshop was organised to gather insights from stakeholders to inform the design of an Analytical Interface Toolkit (AIT). The AIT is a key component of the RLA project.

Key intended outcomes of the workshop were:

- Identifying the requirements of potential end users (including research managers, commercialisation officers, and other stakeholders) for the RLA platform's query and analytical tools.
- The collection of insights into how research data is accessed, visualised, and utilised for decision-making across sectors including academia, government, and industry.

Insights

The following end user requirements were identified:

- 1. Finding Collaborators and Experts:** There is a strong desire to identify potential collaborators, both internal and external to organisations, to enhance research capabilities and secure funding.
- 2. Funding insights:** Participants want insights into funding opportunities, industry contributions, and successful grant applications to inform their strategies and initiatives.
- 3. Benchmarking and Metrics:** There was an identified need for data-driven insights to assess research performance and to compare with competitors.

4. **Identifying Gaps and Strengths:** Participants wish to pinpoint strengths and gaps within their organisation and amongst researchers, particularly regarding industry-partnered projects.
5. **Understanding Collaboration Dynamics:** Participants seek clarity around successful collaborations, including what constitutes a successful industry-partnered project.
6. **Access to comprehensive data:** Participants desire more comprehensive data on funding, collaborations, and expertise beyond internal sources, including insights on university partnerships and industry engagement.

How these insights are incorporated into future work

Figure 1 Funders by field of research

The insights gained from the User Requirements Workshop were incorporated across various aspects of the dashboard proof-of-concept. Two views are highlighted below as notable examples. Sensitive information has been redacted.

In the first view, **Figure 1**, the user can select a combination of year and quarter, as well as a field of research, which is mapped directly with the Australian Research Council's (ARC) Field of Research Classification. The view shows insights about funding, metrics on gaps and strengths, and comprehensive funding data data. This view is informed by workshop insights **2, 3, 4, and 6**.

Figure 2 Researchers who work with other researchers from a selected organisation, on a grant

In the second view, **Figure 2**, users can select to see either Griffith University-linked or external researchers, and then an external organisation. A network graph of the selected organisation, the research funding associated with it, and then the researchers (either within organisation, or external) associated is displayed, along with tabular representations of the grant and research data. This view is informed by workshop insights **1, 2, 3, 4, 5** and **6**.

Demonstration

Workshop

About the workshop

The first Dashboard and Large Language Model demonstration workshop occurred on Friday, the 11th of November 2024. It involved participants from Griffith University, UTS, SCU, and the ARDC.

The purpose of the workshop was to demonstrate progress in the Research Link Australia project, through a showcase of the Analytical Interface Toolkit (AIT), built in Power BI, along with progress in Large Language Models to create a Generative AI for querying the data.

Key outcomes of the workshop were:

- Demonstration of progress in the creation of AIT and LLM, in line with project goals.
- Discussion of technical aspects of Power BI for use in the project, including advantages and disadvantages.
- Solicitation of feedback on the AIT features.

Insights

The following feedback was identified:

1. The AIT User Interface (UI) is well presented and easy to use.

2. The AIT requires further refinement to match specific use cases (for example, as a performance measurement tool, or as a capability finding tool).
3. Power BI as the technical facilitation of the proof-of-concept has advantages in security and access control, but disadvantages in re-querying and the inflexibility of the underlying data model.
4. The LLM and associated Generative AI is a promising direction as a proof-of-concept, but greater capability is presently prohibited by material cost.

How these insights are incorporated into future work

Future work will continue to use the same UI features as present in the current proof-of-concept (*workshop insight 1*). Refinement of the proof-of-concept into separate AITs for identified use cases will commence (*workshop insight 2*). Power BI will continue to be used for the AIT until or unless an open source solution with appropriate access controls is sourced, or data is redacted for sensitive records (*workshop insight 3*). Work will continue on the LLM and Generative AI at current scale, and pending future funding will be expanded in capability (*workshop insight 4*).

Conclusion and

Future Direction

The workshops conducted for the RLA project have provided invaluable insights into user requirements and validated the initial design of the AIT. Stakeholders emphasised the importance of finding collaborators, benchmarking research performance, and accessing comprehensive data for strategic decision-making. Demonstrations of the AIT and LLM capabilities were well received, with constructive feedback guiding refinements for specific use cases.

Looking ahead, the next steps for the project include:

- Refining the AIT to address distinct use cases such as performance measurements and capability identification.
- Continued development of the LLM and Generative AI features, scaling their capabilities as funding enables.
- Strengthening engagement with stakeholders through iterative feedback loops to ensure the tool aligns with evolving user needs.

By implementing these steps, the RLA project will further its mission to foster research collaboration and innovation across Australia, driving impactful outcomes in academia, government, and beyond.

